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D3.5 VITALISE SDK Manual

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
SDK	Software Development Kit
API	Application Programming Interface
RE-API	Remote Execution API
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous deployment
OOP	Object Oriented Programming
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier

Abstract

This is a companion document to the online software development kit (SDK) documentation deliverable itself. It contains a snapshot of the SDK documentation at the time of delivery (it will be updated as technological development advances) and a description of the process followed to select the suitable SDK documentation tools for this use case scenario. It also includes a description of the general researcher workflow to use the VITALISE SDK. Currently the SDK only applies for the Python language, and it is based on the object oriented paradigm (OOP) paradigm and abstract classes. For the documentation generation we have chosen sphinx with automatic documentation generation from docstrings and markdown. And for making the manual available, we have chosen Gitlab pages and Gitlab's continuous integration – deployment (CI-CD) to keep the documentation updated.

The updated online SDK manual is available at: <https://vitalise-project-group.gitlab.io/bayaz/>

Executive summary

This is a deliverable of type OTHER, containing the SDK manual for VITALISE.

The first part of the document describes the general workflow for the researcher making use of the VITALISE SDK. This includes the process of searching for suitable data in the discovery portal, developing the analysis script locally and running the script in the research analysis identifier (RAI) node.

Then the report illustrates the SDK itself (containing a static version while the most updated version will be only maintained at the online SDK manual). This is a combination of manual documentation and a summary of the docstring included in the source code.

Finally, it closes by presenting a discussion about the most suitable SDK dissemination tools for the VITALISE SDK and the chosen option. From the different options available, we have followed the criteria of simplicity and availability, to facilitate the process of keeping the manual updated and easily available.

The updated online SDK manual is available at: <https://vitalise-project-group.gitlab.io/bayaz/>

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable is described as OTHER in the grant agreement, and it relates to Task 3.9 “VITALISE SDKs”. The document describes how to use the remote execution API in Python and how this documentation and related tools will be made public after reviewing several deployment options.

The updated online SDK manual is available at: <https://vitalise-project-group.gitlab.io/bayaz/>

1.2 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the workflow researchers need to follow to use the SDK and run remote experiments.
- Section 3 contains a description for how to execute scripts for development activities following the software interfaces defined for the corresponding purpose.
- Section 4 describes the process followed to select the most appropriate tools for the generation and dissemination of the SDK documentation.
- Section 5 presents some conclusions about the deliverable.

2 Researchers' workflow to use the SDK

2.1 Introduction

This manual describes how to proceed in order to carry out analytics procedures using data from RAI nodes, exposed through the discovery portal.

The workflow representing the classic workflow of a researcher is as described in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Representation of the typical workflow involving a researcher using the RAI SDK . Boxes in green are steps to be carried out by the researcher. Boxes in dashed grey refer to processes carried internally by the discovery portal and the RAI node.

2.2 Step 1: Search for data in the Discovery Portal

Researchers use their own credentials to log in the Discovery Portal, where they can browse through the available datasets. Once they find the most suitable dataset and filtering parameters

(i.e., data query), they can make a data request, which will generate a unique identifier for the query, and will trigger the generation of a synthetic dataset (Figure 2).

Metadata

Select	N/A	Title	Description	RAI Node Server Host	Link
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	#1	dataset test2	dataset test2	41f31c07-659e-4b05-8106-8a3704e79030	GO TO DATASET
<input type="checkbox"/>	#2	dataset test2	dataset test3	41f31c07-659e-4b05-8106-8a3704e79030	GO TO DATASET
<input type="checkbox"/>	#3	dataset test2	dataset test2	41f31c07-659e-4b05-8106-8a3704e79030	GO TO DATASET
<input type="checkbox"/>	#4	Test dataset v1	Test dataset v1	41f31c07-659e-4b05-8106-8a3704e79030	GO TO DATASET
<input type="checkbox"/>	#5	test	test	4ae4b106-0e89-453c-b107-02807aeec177	GO TO DATASET

REQUEST SYNTHETIC DATA GENERATION

Figure 2: Example of synthetic data generation request and resulting dataset

The unique iID and synthetic data generation processes are computationally intensive; therefore, they will be executed asynchronously. Researchers can see when this synthetic dataset has been generated, including a download URL so that they can work with it on their own computer (Figure 2). The unique ID will identify the dataset query defined by the researcher.

2.3 Step 2: Develop/test algorithm locally using synthetic data

The researcher uses the download URL for the synthetic dataset which resembles the real data (s)he wants to work with. This downloaded asset set contains a list of files, one pair per source dataset, including:

- Synthetic data, either in CSV or JSON format.
- An info.json file with the following contents: the synthetic data generation request ID, the name of the dataset, a hash identifying the result of the data query in the remote node containing real data (to run remote execution in a later phase), a description of the dataset and the timestamp.

Example of info.json file:

```
{
  "sd_request_id": "0fc9fa14-f9b9-457a-8ebe-7cf72fc50967",
  "hash_query_real": "1dc879fa14-f9b9-457a-9ebe-7cf95fc50967",
  "description": "SD generated for steps measurements",
  "timestamp": "2022-02-28 16:20:39.597000"
}
```

The researcher uses the Remote execution API (see section 3) to design its code script. In practice, it implies that the researcher needs to generate the following files:

- Requirements.txt: which contains all the external Python packages required for the code to run, following the “pip” file format¹.
- Experiment_config.yaml: which includes metadata for the experiment execution. Currently the file contains the Python version, the data query hash (which must be ID contained in the hash_query_real field from the info.json file) and the data format used.

¹ <https://pip.pypa.io/en/stable/reference/requirements-file-format/>

- MyExperiment.py: which contains the code to be executed, following the SDK approach described in section 3.

2.4 Step 3: Algorithm execution in the RAI node with real data

Once the researchers ensure that their code (MyExperiment.py) runs properly on the local synthetic data, (s)he can upload the code so that it can be run by the RAI node using the real data. To do so, a simple form permits uploading the generated files as shown in Figure 3.

VITALISE Discovery Experiment RAI Node Logout

Search SEARCH

Run Experiment

Specify Parameters

Provide Experiment .py file: No file chosen

Provide Experiment configuration .yaml file: No file chosen

Provide Requirements .txt file: No file chosen

Experiment Description:

Figure 3: RAI node execution request

After the researcher pushes the “RUN EXPERIMENT” button, the algorithm will run in the RAI node on the real query data and it will return the results generated by the script, which can be downloaded through the same web interface.

3 Programmers guide for remote script execution API on Python

The remote execution API (RE-API) is based on the object-oriented programming (OOP) paradigm. Programmers using this RE-API implement a script which contains a class inheriting the RunnerInterface and implementing its methods. Additionally, the RE-API provides classes to read the input data of their query in either tabular (CSV) or JSON based format and classes to return the result of the script, so it can be registered and obtained by the programmers once it is executed in the RAI node. The next schema represents this approach (Figure 4)

Figure 4: API usage schema

The Dataset API provides access to the data transparently between the synthetic data and the real data in the RAI node. Developers implement and debug their code locally using synthetic data. And once the code is running properly, it can be sent to the RAI node, so that it can be run using real data (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Script implementation, testing and deployment

3.1 DataSet API

The DataSet API provides two different classes to access query data:

- DataJson: it provides a dictionary following the JSON structure of the query data.
- DataCsv: it provides a pandas DataFrame object to access the query data.

In both cases, the classes provide the next members:

- Data: containing the data as an object.
- Name: the name of the data object.

3.2 ExperimentRunner interface

Each experiment running a script must inherit the `AbstractExperimentRunner` and implement its `run_code` method, where the developer must use the `DataSet` API to read the query data and use the `StoreResults` API to store the algorithm results.

3.3 StoreResults API

The `StoreResults` class permits storing the script results for the RAI node registry. This class contains these member variables to be filled by the programmer of the script:

- `Data`: contains the result data.
- `Tag`: a descriptive text for the output.

4 SDK manual generation and dissemination tools

4.1 SDK definition

We will consider a Software Development Kit, SDK from now on, as an adaptation of the Wikipedia definition («Software Development Kit», 2022): *...A software development kit (SDK) is a collection of software development tools in one installable package. They facilitate the creation of applications by having a compiler, debugger and sometimes a software framework. They are normally specific to a hardware platform and operating system combination. To create applications with advanced functionalities such as advertisements, push notifications, etc; most application software developers use specific software development kits...*

The VITALISE SDK has the following characteristics:

- It is not a single installable package, since it is not directly installable, but it can be obtained as a single package, using a publicly shared code, documentation and example repository and web page.
- It is currently limited to the Python programming language.
- It is composed of:
 - Source code of the libraries and library packaging scripts.
 - Code documentation.
 - General programmer documentation.
 - Code examples.

4.2 SDK manual requirements

To promote the use of VITALISE SDK, the consortium believes that these are the key requirements:

- Easy access: providing web-based access to documentation, code and examples.
- Easy extension: using software tracking system and standard web technologies to promote third party collaboration.
- Dynamic and example oriented: providing multiple practical use examples with code.
- Reuse of the/a current technology stack for SDK development.
- Permit the inclusion of general documentation, code documentation, examples, and tutorials.

4.3 Tool review

The review of the tool has been carried out in two directions. First, reviewing the elements in Figure 6, which were from an early version survey. Second, by checking alternatives to those tools. And finally, trying to match the current technology stack being used in VITALISE.

Category	Tool	managed content	Tool page	Description / main features
wiki	Gollum	generic text	https://github.com/gollum/gollum	Creates wiki pages from different markup languages. It is backed by a git repository. Provides editor. It is the technology behind github wikis and gitlab wikis.
wiki	MediaWiki	generic text	https://www.mediawiki.org/	Creates wiki pages using the mediawiki language. Provides editor. It is the technology behind Wikipedia.
static page	Jekyll	All hypertext-based content	https://jekyllrb.com/	Creates static pages from markdown and html content. It can be used in conjunction with git. It is the tool behind github pages.
static page	GitBook	All hypertext-based content	https://www.gitbook.com/	Creates static pages from markdown. Its backend is a git repository. Has embedded edit functionality
static page	DocuSaurus	All hypertext-based content	https://docusaurus.io/	Creates static pages from markdown. Its backend is a git repository. Customizable with ReactJS and content plugins
Search engine	DocSearch	index	https://docsearch.algolia.com/	Indexes documentation making it searchable.
learning platform	Moodle	courses, tutorials, examples	https://moodle.org/	multilingual learning platform oriented to create, host, manage and run courses.
learning platform	Open edX	courses, tutorials, examples	https://openedx.org/	The technology behind EdX. Create, host, manage and execute online courses.
specific	Terminologue	Glossary	https://www.terminologue.org/	Centralised multilingual terminology manager
Library	Matplotlib	Multimedia - visualization	https://matplotlib.org/	Matplotlib is a comprehensive library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in Python.
Library	bokeh	Multimedia - visualization	https://docs.bokeh.org/	a Python library for creating interactive JavaScript visualizations for modern web browsers.
Desktop	OBS	Multimedia - video	https://obsproject.com/	Used mostly by streamers, combining pc screen with webcam feeds. It can be a useful tool to record tutorials, examples, and walkthroughs.
Desktop	stepguide	walkthrough	https://www.stepguide.io/	Chrome Extension records you using your web applications and automatically creates a guide, allows you to edit and then share it on the web.
Desktop	Scribe	walkthrough	https://get.scribehq.com/process-documentation/	Automatically generates a visual step-by-step guide, ready to share
Auto generated	redoc	API	https://redocly.com/redoc/	Creates and hosts an interactive web page from OpenAPI definition. Offers API documentation, API experimentation, and generates code snippets ready to be used.
Auto generated	Doxygen	Code documentation, general text	https://www.doxygen.nl/	is the de facto standard tool for generating documentation from annotated source code in different languages. Generates static pages, integrates with IDEs.
Auto generated	Read the Docs	Code documentation, general text	https://readthedocs.org/	Integrates with git repositories to provide automatic source code versioned documentation automatically

Figure 6: Survey post based SDK documentation options

A review of Figure 6 clearly shows some patterns. We can see that, regardless of the technology used, these are the main options:

- Using tools to automatically generate source code documentation from previously annotated source code.
- Using tools to facilitate media and interactive based course, tutorial generation
- Creating a web page (e.g., wiki).
- Using tools to make a bridge between code repository, documentation generation and documentation publish as web pages.

4.4 Details of the selected approach

For the VITALISE SDK, we need a combination of all options, so that we fulfil with the requirements defined. To the knowledge of the authors, there is no single tool which provides all these features. Therefore, we propose the next set of tools to cover all the features:

- For automatic code documentation generation, we propose using Sphinx (*Welcome — Sphinx documentation*, s. f.), given its maturity (cleaner than DOxygen), features and good interaction with the Python language.
- For the time being, when the generation of media and interactive courses is not foreseen, we propose the use of OBS (*Open Broadcaster Software | OBS*, s. f.) for short and simple tutorials. And, if necessary, we propose the use of Moodle (*Moodle - Open-source learning platform | Moodle.org*, s. f.)
- To create a main web page and make the bridge between code and documentation generation to access the entire SDK, we propose the use of Gitlab and Gitlab pages, given that VITALISE technology stack includes Gitlab for code versioning and development. This option is also compatible with the use of Sphinx² and it facilitates the automatic update and deployment of the SDK.

The workflow for documenting the code and deploying the manual is as follows (Figure 7):

1. Software engineers create/update the manual by creating and updating files in the git repository:
 - a. Documenting the code using docstring³.
 - b. Producing additional documentation pages in Markdown⁴
 - c. Editing SDK usage examples in Jupyter Notebook⁵
2. Each time there is a push in the designated git branch, the manual is updated and deployed using Gitlab's CI/CD utils:
 - a. Sphinx generates HTML combining the docstrings, markdown files and the Jupyter notebooks.
 - b. The resulting web is deployed to Gitlab pages, thanks to Gitlab CI-CD⁶.

² <https://gitlab.com/pages/sphinx>

³ <https://peps.python.org/pep-0257/>

⁴ <https://daringfireball.net/projects/markdown/>

⁵ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁶ <https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/>

Figure 7: Manual generation and deploy workflow

4.4.1 Sphinx

Sphinx facilitates producing code documentation in several formats, such as html from Python source code files documented, using docstrings in code and additional documentation files written in markup languages. Although it was originally designed to be used with reStructuredText⁷ markup language for richer documentation, thanks to the use of extension, it can also produce documentation from other sources such as Markdown files, and Jupyter Notebook files.

4.4.2 Gitlab pages

Given that the remote execution API source code is published as a Gitlab project, we can take advantage of Gitlab Pages. As the tool web states: *...With GitLab Pages, you can publish static websites directly from a repository in GitLab (GitLab Pages | GitLab, s. f.)*

Gitlab provides its own hosting address, but it can also link to external web domains. Deployment is controlled by the Gitlab CI/CD tools, therefore permitting the automatic update.

⁷ <https://docutils.sourceforge.io/rst.html>

5 Conclusions

This document has presented a summary of the SDK manual as well as the process to generate it after a state-of-the-art review, regarding tools for its generation and deployment.

The tool review revealed that there is not any single solution for all use cases, but many tools which can be used in combination, tailored to every specific requirement. The following three tools were determined to be of primary importance to our project.

Sphinx seems to be the de facto tool for documenting Python code. It offers plenty of flexibility and extensions, but the learning curve can be a bit steep. Additionally, due to the need to use third-party extensions for a proper deployment, it can be quite complicated to configure and thus obtain the desired result. On the other hand, it generates beautiful static web sites from code and documentation files including search and indexing features with ease.

Gitlab pages greatly facilitates the deployment, but it is focused only on static web pages. And it requires an external web domain to have a meaningful URL. On the other hand, it is very convenient, and it is also easy to configure access permission.

Jupyter notebooks offer a clean and descriptive way to share code snippets as well as code examples.

The deployment part of the SDK manual workflow could be reused for other programming languages. But, regarding the web-based documentation generation, alternative tools would be required, such as Doxygen.

6 References

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